

PVC membrane ion selective electrodes for determination of cationic surfactants

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Abstract : Two membrane electrodes were prepared, using sodium perchlorate-Aliquot 336, an ion-pair complex as electro-active material for one electrode and tetradecyl trimethyl ammonium bromide-sodium tetraphenyl borate as electro-active material in case of second electrode. The first electrode exhibits linear response for the surfactant cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide in the concentration range 1×10^{-1} to 5×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³ with slope as 61.5 mV/decade change in the concentration and the second electrode exhibits linear response for the surfactant *n*-tetradecyl trimethyl ammonium bromide in the concentration range 2.5×10^{-3} to 1×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³ with slope 54.6 mV/decade. The working pH range and the response time for the first electrode is 4–10 and 15 s respectively while for electrode second the values are 2.5 to 6.5 and 30 s respectively. Selectivity coefficients for several cations have been determined.

Keywords : Surfactant, ion-selective electrodes, cationic surfactants.

Introduction

Surfactants as environmental pollutants are present in various samples, including natural and waste water. Initially the determination of different surfactants was confined to titration techniques and spectrophotometry^{1–3}. Later on chromatographic, electrochemical techniques and improved spectrophotometric methods have been employed. The Vytras group^{4,5} and those from Moody and Thomas^{6–8} did pioneering work towards the development of selective electrodes for determination of surfactants. The interest towards determination of surfactants using selective electrodes continues to grow^{9–19}

Mahajan and others have reported cationic surfactant selective potentiometric sensors²⁰. These sensors had barrel configuration with inner reference solutions. Madunic-Cacic and others reported determination of cationic surfactants (cetylpyridinium chloride (CPC), hexadecyl trimethyl ammonium bromide (CTAB) and Hyamine) in pharmaceutical disinfectants using another barrel shaped sensor²¹. One of the sensors developed by Mahajan *et al.* is based on neutral ion pair carrier complex of tetradecyl trimethyl ammonium dodecyl sulphate TTA⁺-DS⁻ which was used for the determination of TTA⁺. The sensor developed by Madunic-Cacic *et al.* is based on complex

of 1,3-didecyl-2-methyl-imidazolium cation with tetraphenyl borate antagonist ion. This sensor was used for the determination of CPC, CTAB and Hyamine.

In present work we have developed two new PVC membrane ion selective electrodes, one is for determination CTA⁺ which is based on ion-pair complex (Aliquot 336-sodium perchlorate) as an electroactive material and second electrode is based on TTA⁺-TPB⁻ ion-pair complex as an electroactive material for the determination of TTA⁺.

Results and discussion

Electrode response :

The response of electrode I was evaluated by taking different concentrations of the cationic surfactants, cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide (CTAB) and by recording the millivolt (mV) values for each solution using the electrode I as an indicator electrode and an external reference electrode (Ag, AgCl). A fairly linear response in the concentration range 1×10^{-1} – 5×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³ was observed. A number of solutions of another cationic surfactant, tetradecyl trimethyl ammonium bromide (TTAB) were also prepared in the concentration range 1×10^{-1} – 1×10^{-6} mol dm⁻³ and the response of each solution was

recorded using electrode II as indicator electrode and a silver/silver chloride electrode as reference electrode. A fairly linear electrode response was observed in the concentration range 2.5×10^{-3} – 1×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³.

Response time :

To find out the response time of two electrodes (I and II), two different solutions of respective surfactant were prepared and the concentration of one was ten times higher than the other. Then the respective electrodes were dipped into the solution of the higher concentration and after equilibration the potential was measured. Thereafter electrodes were drawn from solution of higher concentration and immediately dipped in the solution of lower concentration. The potential was now recorded at the intervals of 5 s. A constant potential was obtained after 15 s and 30 s for electrode I and II respectively (Fig. 1).

Effect of pH :

In order to study the effect of pH on electrode response, a number of solutions were prepared with a fixed concentration (0.01 mol dm⁻³) of each surfactant over a pH range 2 to 12 and potential of these solutions was recorded with the help of electrode I and II and a silver/

silver chloride electrode. It was observed that the electrode potential remains unchanged over a pH range of 4 to 10 for electrode I and 2.5 to 6.5 for electrode II (Fig. 2). Thus the working pH ranges for two electrodes are 4–10 and 2.5–6.5 respectively.

Selectivity coefficients :

The influence of the interferences on the response of the surfactant sensors is described by the Nikolski-Eisenman equation :

$$E = E^0 + RT/ZF \ln [a_i + K_{ij} (a_j)^{Z/Y}]$$

where K_{ij} is the selectivity coefficient, Z is the charge on primary ion, Y is the charge on interfering ion, a_i and a_j are the activities of primary ion and interfering ion respectively. The mixed solution method^{22,23} was used for measurement of selectivity coefficient, because it yields more realistic data than the separate solution method for the system investigated. The sensor response was measured for a series of solutions of varying primary ion activity a_i and fixed interfering ion activity a_j . The potentials were plotted against activity of primary ion. The selectivity coefficients were calculated from the intersection of activities of the ions at the break point from the

Fig. 1. Response time for electrode I and II.

Fig. 2. Effect of pH for electrode I and II.

graph, using the following relationship.

$$K_{ij} = (a_i)_{\text{intersection}} / (a_j)^{Z_i/Y}$$

The selectivity coefficients of cations studied are summarized in Table 1 for both the electrodes I and II respectively.

The above mentioned characteristics for the electrodes

are summarized in Table 2, which reveals that both the electrodes have excellent detection limits and longer pH-range with comparatively small response time. The response of electrode one and electrode two are being compared with the electrodes reported in the literature (Table 3). From Table it is clear that electrodes developed for cationic surfactants are better than the electrodes reported

Table 1. Selectivity coefficients (K_{ij} where i is primary ion and j is the interfering ion) for electrode one and two

Interferent	Selectivity coefficient (K_{ij})	
	Electrode I	Electrode II
Na ⁺	2.0×10^{-2}	4.5×10^{-2}
Mn ²⁺	4.6×10^{-3}	5.7×10^{-4}
Cu ²⁺	2.5×10^{-3}	5.0×10^{-4}
Fe ²⁺	3.2×10^{-3}	9.1×10^{-4}
Zn ²⁺	2.0×10^{-3}	7.1×10^{-4}
Ni ²⁺	2.2×10^{-3}	4.0×10^{-4}
Ca ²⁺	1.7×10^{-3}	3.5×10^{-4}
Cr ³⁺	5.0×10^{-4}	1.71×10^{-4}
TTA ⁺	0.63	-
CTA ⁺		0.4

Table 2. Characteristics of surfactant ion selective membrane electrodes

Parameter	Electrode I	Electrode II
Slope (mV decade ⁻¹)	61.5	54.6
Correlation coefficient (r^2)	0.998	0.996
Linear range (mol dm ⁻³)	1×10^{-1} - 5×10^{-5}	2.5×10^{-3} - 1×10^{-5}
Response time (s)	15	30
Working pH range	4-10	2.5-6.5

Table 3. Comparison of response range of cationic surfactants

Sl. no.	Species	Detection range (mol dm ⁻³)		Ref.
		This work	Literature work	
1.	CTAB	5×10^{-5} - 1×10^{-1}	2×10^{-6} - 1×10^{-4}	21
2.	TTAB	1×10^{-5} - 2.5×10^{-3}	3.98×10^{-5} - 1.93×10^{-3}	20

in the literature as these electrodes have larger working range.

Experimental

Materials and apparatus :

Analytical grade cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide (CTAB, Fluka) and *n*-tetradecyl trimethyl ammonium bromide (TTAB, Lancaster) were used without any purification. Aliquot 336 (Lancaster), sodium perchlorate (CDH), sodium tetraphenyl borate (Lancaster), benzene (Qualigens Excelar), polyvinyl chloride (PVC) (Sigma), tetrahydrofuran (THF) (BDH), dioctylphthalate (DOP) and ethanol (Bengal Chemicals and Pharmaceuticals Ltd.) were used as received. All the solutions were prepared in double distilled water. A Century CP (901) pH meter with a silver/silver chloride electrode as reference electrode was used. All measurements were made at room temperature (25 ± 2 °C).

Preparation of electrode I :

0.5 g of sodium perchlorate was dissolved in water and 0.5 g of surfactant (Aliquot 336) was dissolved in 5 mL of benzene. Both the solutions were poured into the separatory funnel. After shaking, the separatory funnel was kept in stand for 30 min. There after organic phase, which contains surfactant-perchlorate complex, was separated and was used as an electroactive material.

250 mg PVC and 500 mg electroactive material was dissolved in 5 mL of tetrahydrofuran (THF) in a 50 mL beaker and added 100 mg plasticizer (dioctylphthalate) and mixed with constant stirring. The resulting solution was poured in a casting tube and left for 24 h for drying to obtain a master membrane. A piece of membrane was cut and fixed at lower end of barrel shaped glass tube with the help of epoxy resin (Araldite, Ciba-Geigy) and dried for 48 h. The tube was then filled with reference solution having concentration 0.01 mol dm^{-3} of CTAB. The whole assembly was dipped in a solution of 0.1 mol dm^{-3} of CTAB such that membrane portion was dipped. The tube was then allowed to stand in the solution for 5 days. The silver/silver chloride electrode, was used as an internal reference electrode.

Preparation of electrode II :

The electroactive material for fabrication of a second electrode was prepared from interaction of equimolar

amount of *n*-tetradecyl trimethyl ammonium bromide (TTAB) and sodium tetraphenyl borate (STPB). The resulting white precipitate of the tetradecyl trimethyl ammonium-tetraphenyl borate ($\text{TTA}^+ \text{-TPB}^-$) ion-pair complex was washed repeatedly with water followed by recrystallization from acetone.

The electrode membrane was of the following composition : Dioctylphthalate as plasticizer (200 mg), PVC of high molecular mass (100 mg) and $\text{TTA}^+ \text{-TPB}^-$ ion exchange complex as sensing material (10 mg). This electrode was prepared by using similar procedure as electrode first. This electrode was sensitive for TTA^+ ions.

The entire cell assembly involving these PVC-membrane type electrodes could be represented as :

Internal reference electrode (Ag-AgCl)	Internal reference solution (M^+)	Ion selective membrane	Sample solution	External reference electrode (Ag-AgCl)
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